

A PORTABLE COCHLEAR IMPLANT SIMULATOR AS A LISTENING PROBE FOR MUSIC COMPOSERS

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ABSTRACT

Cochlear implants (CIs) significantly improve speech for individuals but pose challenges for music appreciation due to limited spectral resolution and reduced temporal fine structure encoding. Algorithmic preprocessing techniques for music adaptation aim to work around these limitations by reducing the complexity of music, both in compositional aspect—by emphasizing essential musical elements like rhythm and melody, or in the spectral domain—by reducing spectral complexity. This article explores a novel approach to music adaptation by directly engaging composers. Towards this goal, a real-time portable CI simulator was developed to give composers an idea of how music is perceived by CI users and adapt their compositions accordingly. Three highly experienced composers participated in the study, in which they remixed one of their original songs, while using the CI simulator as a listening probe, monitoring the result through the perception of a CI user. Their remixes were compared with an established music preprocessing technique in a listening test involving six individuals who use CIs. Results suggest that composers intuitively emphasize rhythmic clarity and simplify harmonic content, aligning with established CI preprocessing strategies. Furthermore, the potential of creative human adaptation in enhancing CI music perception provides valuable insights for music accessibility.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cochlear implants (CIs) have significantly improved speech perception for individuals with severe to profound hearing loss [1]. However, music perception remains a major challenge due to the device's limited spectral resolution, reduced temporal fine structure encoding, and inability to fully convey complex harmonic and timbral information [2]. While CI users can generally perceive rhythm, they struggle with melodic and harmonic elements, leading to an impoverished musical experience. Given the emo-

tional and cultural importance of music, enhancing its perception for CI users is a crucial area of research [3].

Several preprocessing techniques have been proposed to optimize music for CI listeners, including spectral reduction [4] and source separation [5]. These methods attempt to enhance music perception by simplifying the signal to match the auditory constraints of CIs. However, such approaches often sacrifice musical richness and may not fully address the subjective and aesthetic aspects of music appreciation. There is a need for alternative strategies that balance perceptual clarity with musical expressiveness.

Another approach is to involve composers in the adaptation of music for CI users. Unlike automated preprocessing methods, composers rely on artistic intuition and on an understanding of musical structure to creatively rework compositions. By directly experiencing music through a CI simulation, composers can adjust musical elements such as melody, harmony, and rhythm to enhance perceptual accessibility while maintaining musical integrity. This human-centered approach could offer new insights into music adaptation and inspire improvements in algorithmic preprocessing.

This study investigates whether composers, when exposed to CI-processed audio, naturally simplify and modify their music in ways that align with known CI preprocessing techniques. We hypothesize that composers will emphasize rhythmic clarity, reduce harmonic complexity, and adjust melodic patterns to improve intelligibility after CI processing and, hence, perceived musical quality for CI users. Our research aims to (1) explore composer perspectives on the limitations imposed by CIs, (2) compare CI-based remixing to standard preprocessing methods, and (3) assess whether composer-adapted music enhances the listening experience for CI users.

2. RELATED WORK

In terms of music preference, Looi et al. [6] found that a group of CI listeners preferred music played by a single instrument over music with multiple instruments. A similar finding was reported by Kohlberg et al. [7], with CI listeners preferring versions of songs with only one to three instruments, as opposed to the original recordings, with multiple instruments. Furthermore, along similar lines,

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Buyens et al. [8] found that CI listeners generally prefer an attenuation of all instruments with respect to the vocals, with piano and guitar being more attenuated than bass and drums. In addition, besides musical factors, such as “clear rhythm”, personal and environmental factors such as “familiar music” and “quiet environment” were found by Lassaletta et al. [9] to improve the experience of music listening for CI users. Multi-sensory integration—in particular, tactile augmentation—was found to enhance music appreciation among this group by Paisa et al. [10], who implemented and evaluated the use of vibrotactile concert furniture to improve the live music experience for people with hearing loss.

The limited number of CI electrodes result in poor spectral resolution and reduced frequency selectivity. Increasing the number of electrodes does not seem to improve neither speech nor music perception, likely due to an over-saturation effect [11]. These limitations in signal transmission within CIs and the consequent distortion, result in a typically unsatisfactory musical experience for most CI users [12].

Music preprocessing techniques aim to reduce the complexity of musical signals by emphasizing essential musical elements such as the main melody and rhythm, attenuating the accompaniment, and reducing harmonic complexity. To this end, several methods for such preprocessing have been developed like: spectral dimensionality reduction [4], harmonic/percussive sound separation (HPSS) [13], music source separation [5] or melody identification [14].

Traditionally, the amount of information transmitted by a CI can be simulated using channel vocoders [15]. These typically consist of two signal processing stages: *Analysis* and *Resynthesis*. In the *Analysis* stage, the input signal is split into a number of audio channels using a bank of bandpass filters. In each channel, the envelope of the signal is extracted and passed to the *Resynthesis* stage, where it is used to modulate an acoustic carrier. These carriers are often sine waves or band-filtered noise which either fail to mimic the broad spread of excitation produced by the electrodes of a CI, as in the case of the former, or, as in the case of the latter, they contain intrinsic modulations which interfere with the modulations of the speech signal they aim to transmit.

With these limitations, research aiming to use alternative acoustic carriers in order to improve the realism of CI vocoder simulations has been carried out [16].

Pulse-spreading harmonic complexes (PSHCs) [17], whose phase relationship between their harmonic complex carriers can be adjusted so that their envelope repetition rate, referred to as pulse rate, can be varied independently of their fundamental frequency (f_0). This pulse rate was optimized to minimize intrinsic modulations after auditory filtering, i.e. after “exciting” the PSHC carrier by filtering it with a gamma-tone filter, which mimics auditory processing. The result of a PSHC carrier at its optimal pulse rate produces a relatively flat envelope at the output of the auditory filter, hence reducing both random and periodic intrinsic modulations. Mesnildrey et al. [18] developed

a vocoder using such PSHCs as carriers, which was later found by Karoui et al. [19] to be judged more similar to the sound of a cochlear implant by single-sided CI listeners, as compared with other vocoders using sine-waves or noise-bands as carriers. Their study was carried out with speech signals. Furthermore, Steinhauer et al. [20] carried out a study with normal hearing (NH) listeners using a similar CI simulator to compare the perception of falling, flat and rising melodic contours. They found that NH individuals using the vocoder with PSHC carriers had similar results in terms of melodic contour identification (MCI) to individuals with CIs.

3. METHODOLOGY

The first step of the current study was the development of a portable state-of-the-art CI simulator that composers can interact with and route through an audio interface to monitor their music as heard by a CI listener. A hardware implementation was preferred to facilitate use in live performance settings and by non-electronic musicians. Detailed implementation information is provided in 3.1.

With the simulator available, composers will listen to a selected piece and adjust various parameters—such as overall equalization and compression—along with the addition or removal of musical components, to produce a remixed version of the original track they deem more suitable for CI listening.

In order to compare the composers’ remixes to established signal pre-processing techniques for enhancing music perception in CI listeners, the original song will also be processed through one of such techniques, as described in more detail in Section 3.2.1. Once the 3 song versions are available: original, remixed and preprocessed, a listening test is carried out with a total of 6 individuals wearing CIs. The test consists of a category comparison rating (CCR) between the different versions, further described in Section 3.3.1. Furthermore, a series of interviews with the composers with a set number of questions are carried out, aiming to qualitatively evaluate their adaptation strategies and perspectives of the remixing process. This is detailed in Section 3.3.2.

A public Github repository has been created where all the code related to the current study is available, i.e. the Bela microcontroller C++ project and all the Python scripts used for both development and evaluation [21].

3.1 CI Simulation Setup

A CI simulator real-time mono audio effect was implemented on the Bela microcontroller¹ and controlled via an AKAI Midimix MIDI interface². The effect is a vocoder, running at a 16 kHz sample rate, with an *Analysis* and a *Resynthesis* stage. It is based on the work of [18] with some modifications.

¹ <https://bela.io/>

² <https://www.akaipro.com/midimix>

3.1.1 Analysis

In the *Analysis* stage the sound is divided into 8 frequency bands between $f_{min} = 200$ Hz and $f_{max} = 7000$ Hz, with the width and center frequency of each band computed using Greenwood functions in order to simulate identically wide cochlear membrane regions [16].

After splitting the sound into 8 channels, each resulting signal is band-pass filtered using 6th order Butterworth filters defined by the frequency edges computed for each analysis bin. This step is followed by envelope extraction, using half-wave rectification followed by low-pass filtering with a 4th order Butterworth filter. The cutoff frequency of this filter is channel dependent, and equivalent to the pulse-rate of the PSHC carrier associated with each channel divided by two [18]. Cutoff frequencies larger than 200 Hz are limited to this value.

3.1.2 Resynthesis

The *Resynthesis* stage takes the envelopes computed in the *Analysis* stage for each analyzed channel, which are then used to modulate the PSHC carriers, filtered through corresponding gamma-tone filters. The fundamental frequency f_0 of the PSHC carriers is set to 1 Hz, as opposed to the 0.3 Hz used by [18]. This value is consistent, however, with the *Original* work by [17] which introduced PSHCs. Using $f_0 = 1$ Hz also means that the PSHCs will be periodic with a period of $T = 1$ s, as opposed to $T = 3.33$ s if $f_0 = 0.3$ Hz is used instead. This is important, as the PSHCs and their auditory filtering via gamma-tone filters are computed offline and uploaded to the Bela at start-up and then read at runtime as wave-tables. For each frequency range in the vocoder channels, the lowest and highest harmonic indices of the PSHCs are computed with a Python adaptation of the original Matlab function³, covering the entire frequency range. The order k of each PSHC results from its optimal pulse-rate (in pulses per second, *pps*) as: $k = \lfloor \sqrt{pps} \rfloor$, with the optimal pulse rate being computed using a second-order polynomial equation which relates it to the center frequency of the PSHC frequency range [18]: $y = 37 + 151x + 0.17x^2$, where y is the optimal pulse rate (in pps) and x is the center frequency.

Using these inputs, the PSHCs are computed for each frequency range in the vocoder's audio channels. These are then filtered with gamma-tone filters centered at the center frequency of these ranges. Note that the center frequency is chosen as the geometric mean, to more accurately reflect the "middle" frequency in the logarithmic space of audio frequency perception.

The generation of PSHCs involves some random assignment of the phases of each harmonic, and in order to avoid intrinsic modulations associated with this randomness, a total of 50 random instances of PSHCs filtered with gamma-tone filters are saved as wave-tables for each audio channel. Then, in the real-time implementation on the Bela, these will be cycled through randomly.

With the *Resynthesis* carriers available, the extracted envelopes from the *Analysis* stage are used to modulate their

Figure 1. Setup and wiring of the CI Simulator real-time audio effect, implemented on the Bela microcontroller and controlled via an AKAI Midimix MIDI interface.

amplitude. Furthermore, the root mean square (RMS) of the resulting amplitude-modulated signals is computed for each channel in each real-time processing block, and only the six channels with the highest RMS values are used for synthesizing the final output.

Finally, the levels of the six audio channels (with the highest RMS) are equalized to the corresponding levels of the analysis band-pass filters, before being added to produce the final output.

3.1.3 Interface layout

The setup of the audio effect and its wiring can be seen in Figure 1. The Bela is powered via its mini USB port, then the MIDI interface is connected to the Bela. The audio in/out on the board can be connected with 3.5 mm jack adapters. There are two adjustable parameters in the CI simulator effect, an input gain and an output gain, controlled via the MIDI interface with the top left rotating knob and the bottom right vertical slider. The upper row of LEDs above the 8 channel vertical sliders light up yellow to illustrate which of the six vocoder channels are "active" at a given moment (based on the RMS selection, as per the previous section). The channels are in the order of the lowest frequency range to highest from left to right. Moreover, to avoid clipping and consequent distortion of the audio effect, the bottom row of LEDs light up red if the magnitude at that corresponding channel is greater than 0.5. Technically, this is not clipping per se, but it is large enough that when added with the contribution of the other channels, it could cause clipping. If the final output clips (the summed up channels), i.e. its magnitude is larger than 1, the second LED above the Master vertical slider lights up.

3.2 Composer Experiment

Three composers have participated in the study, each with different musical expertise. They were first introduced to the CI simulator audio effect, and they all familiarized themselves with its sound by listening to various musical pieces with it, both their own and others. Once they gained some intuitive control of the effect, they chose one of their

³<http://www.daima.lma.cnrs-mrs.fr/pshc.html>

Figure 2. Sketch of the remixing process carried out by the composers in order to produce a remixed song of one of their *Original* pieces, adapted for CI listening, named *CI Remixed*.

pieces, from here on named *Original*, and then proceeded to create a remixed version of it, adapted for CI listening, from here forth named *CI Remixed*. During the remixing process the audio was routed via a Allen & Heath ZEDi-10 mixer both to main speakers as well as to the CI simulator audio in. This allowed them to monitor the CI simulated sound, i.e. the audio out of the effect via headphones. A sketch of the process is given in Figure 2. The composers and their individual approach to the remixing process are introduced in the following.

Alberto Novello⁴ is professor of electronic music at the Conservatory of Padova, Italy. Drawing on his experience, he quickly understood the study’s research question, having already had a basic understanding of how a CI works. He chose a recently composed piece, so he had fresh memory of it and, for the remixing process, decided to operate on his preferred DAW, Ableton Live, with the FabFilter Q3 visual equalizer. The piece is quite experimental and full of rich tones and rhythmic elements, as well as classic electronic music effects like resonant sweeps.

Giorgio Pacorig⁵ is professor of jazz piano at the Conservatory of Trieste, Italy. He decided to listen to a piece he recently recorded with a jazz quartet (piano, bass, drums, reeds) played from a DAW he is familiar with. Adjusting the EQ levels, he did not appreciate any modification on the piece, thus he decided he could have more room of intervention with a single-instrument track, rooted in rhythmic figures. Switching to a piano solo improvisation from his discography, that he knows really well, he processed it in the WaveLab software by adjusting the Waves Q10 parametric equalizer. After several iterations, he thought that the only way to appreciate some modification to sound was to push to overdrive some frequency bands. He felt pretty unsatisfied but beforehand he thought it would have been more functional to play an electric instrument (i.e., Fender Rhodes) so to have more sounds parameters to change.

Giovanni Maier⁶ is professor of jazz double bass at the Conservatory of Trieste, Italy. He asked to listen to a CI simulator processed track of one of his pieces beforehand.

⁴ <https://siapd.conservatoriodimusica.it/docenti/view/81>

⁵ <https://conts.it/it/bio/giorgio-pacorig/>

⁶ <https://conts.it/it/bio/giovanni-maier/>

Upon receiving it, there was a discussion about the possibilities of a CI, of current state-of-the-art implants and the whole purpose of the research. He did not operate on a DAW usually, except for some cut-and-paste edits, thus he decided to directly act on his own instrument, playing a song from himself with the CI simulator processed sound on headphones. So his approach was different in an interesting way compared with the other two composers, as well as different with respect to the remixing process sketch in Figure 2, by skipping the audio output from the Main Speakers and playing his instrument live, while hearing only the CI simulation of its sound via the headphones.

3.2.1 Standard pre-processing of Original song

An important part of the current study is to compare the results of the remixing process carried out by the composers with other established methods for pre-processing of music signals aiming to enable higher appraisal and enjoyment of music by CI users.

The method chosen for comparison is a combination of harmonic/percussive source separation (HPSS) and spectral dimensionality reduction via principal component analysis (PCA). This method was found to be more suitable for a wider range of music genres [22] as compared with PCA or HPSS alone. In particular, the signal is split into its *Percussive* (P) and *Harmonic* (H) components using HPSS. The next step involves taking the *Harmonic* signal and applying a spectral reduction algorithm. This consists in applying PCA to a constant-Q (CQT) transformation representation of the signal, and reconstructing it using an inverse CQT, from a low-rank approximation of the CQT, based on only the first eight principal components [23]. This combination of methods is termed $H_{PCA(8)+P}$ in [22].

For the three *Original* songs of each composer, the $H_{PCA(8)+P}$ pre-processing method was applied to produce 3 new versions of the songs, henceforth named *CI Preprocessed*.

The $H_{PCA(8)+P}$ implementation was carried out in Python, using mainly the librosa library, with native functions like *hps*, *cqt* and *icqt* tuned to match parameters described in [11, 22].

Figure 3 shows a comparison of the CQT magnitudes for a 10 second excerpt of Alberto Novello’s *Original* track and the corresponding *CI Preprocessed* and *CI Remixed* versions. It can be seen that the *CI Preprocessed* version shows reduced energy in the higher frequency, while preserving the low-energy frequencies, when compared to the *Original*. This is expected as PCA-based spectral complexity reduction identifies and preserves spectral components with the highest signal power and attenuates spectral ranges with lower power. It must be noted, however, that for all three *Original* compositions, the PCA performed on the CQT magnitude of their *Harmonic* signals revealed that the first eight principal components accounted for over 85% of the total variance. Consequently, the reconstruction was consistently quite accurate. The *CI Remixed* version on the other hand shows a reduction in the energy content of the lower frequencies while preserving or amplify-

Figure 3. Comparison of the CQT magnitude for an excerpt of the *Original* song by Alberto Novello and the CQT magnitudes of the corresponding *CI Preprocessed* as well as the *CI Remixed* versions.

ing the energy of some of the higher frequency notes. This comparison was observed also when looking at the 2 other compositions and their corresponding CI adapted versions. In particular, in Giovanni Maier’s case, a shortening of the notes, highlighting their percussive part was observed.

3.3 Evaluation Process

The evaluation process is based on a subjective listening test of the 3 different versions of the songs carried out by a total of 6 persons with CIs, as well as an open qualitative interview with the composers, exploring their general impressions and perspective of the remixing process.

3.3.1 Listening Test for CI Users

CI users were recruited by Roberta Rebesco, an audiologist/speech therapist at the Burlo Garofolo Pediatric Institute in Trieste, Italy. They were invited to carry out the listening tests, which were set up online via the Google Forms survey administration software, by means of a questionnaire divided in three sections.

First, they had to accept a privacy notice for personal data, cf. Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council dated 27 April 2016, as well as Legislative Decree 196/03 (“Code on the Protection of Personal Data”).

In the second section they were requested some individual data: age, gender, configuration of their CIs (unilateral, bilateral, bimodal or other), the model of CI/CIs they use, type of deafness (post or prelingual), and duration of use of their CIs. In addition, a number of questions were added, in order to investigate their musical affinity/engagement as well as their general hearing ability with their CIs. These were: “How much do you like listening to music?”, “How often do you listen to music?” and “How well do you hear speech with the cochlear implant(s)?”. These were rated on a Likert scale from “A little” (1) to “A lot” (5).

The final section of the questionnaire was the listening test, which consisted of a total of 12 pairwise comparisons of the *Original*, *CI Remixed* and *CI Preprocessed* songs from the 3 composers. The *Original* songs served as a baseline reference and therefore, the following comparisons were made: *Original* vs *CI Remixed*, *Original* vs *CI*

Preprocessed, *CI Remixed* vs *CI Preprocessed* and *Original* vs *Original*. The order of presentation of the songs was randomized and the CI listeners were requested to rate how much they enjoyed the second song compared to the first (in order of presentation) on a category comparison rating (CCR) discrete scale ranging from “Very little” (-3) to “Very much” (3) and centered at “The same” (0).

An important note is that in order to limit the duration of the tests, only 10 second excerpts of all the songs were selected, matching between the different versions, for each composer. This was carried by the authors of the study, with the permission of the composers.

3.3.2 Composer Interviews

The perspective of music composers with regards to music as experienced through CIs has not been extensively explored in literature, as per the knowledge of the current authors. Ideally, such perspectives would be most welcome from actual CI users, who are also musicians, even on a personal passion level, if not on a professional level. However, CI users who spend many hours engaging in music listening and playing music is rare among the general population of CI users [24].

Gfeller et al. [25] carried out a valuable qualitative and patient-engaged research study analyzing the experiences of six CI users who successfully engage in active music making, through open-ended inquiries and narrative interviews. They found several strategies and factors that CI users may find useful in improving their music experience, some of which are relevant to the current study: selecting accessible sounds, using all senses, music theory exercises, and speech training exercises. These fall in line to some extent with the idea behind music pre-processing for CI listeners, in terms of reduction of spectral complexity and highlighting elements which are more easily perceived with the CI spectral and temporal resolution, such as percussive elements.

The composers who participated in the present study experienced music through a CI simulation, which is itself limited compared to the individual experiences of CI users. Additionally, they were limited to remixing and not composition or improvisation. However, their experience can

still provide valuable insights that could provide inspiration to music adaptation and preprocessing. For this scope, a qualitative interview with a fixed number of questions was sent to each composer. A qualitative analysis of their responses is presented in Section 4.2.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Listening Test for CI Users

A total of 6 individuals with cochlear implants (CIs) participated in the study, with a mean age of 23 years ($SD = 4.43$ years). All participants received their implants during the prelingual stage and had various configurations: two had bilateral CIs, 3 had a unilateral configuration and one had a bimodal setup, with a CI on one side and a hearing aid on the other. In terms of CI models, 3 had devices from Advanced Bionics and 3 from Cochlear, which were implanted at an average age of 2.5 years ($SD = 1.6$ years). All participants showed high appreciation for music (Mean = 4.5 and $SD = 0.76$) and high frequency of listening to music (Mean = 4) with somewhat higher variation ($SD = 1.15$). Similarly their speech understanding was also rated high (Mean = 4 and $SD = 0.81$).

As for the CCR listening test, one subject presented as a clear outlier, rating the reference comparison *Original vs Original* on the highest end of the scale for the song excerpts from the 3 composers. Therefore, it was decided to exclude them from the analysis. Therefore, the final analysis includes five participants.

Figure 4 shows boxplots of similarity ratings for each condition, with individual participant scores overlaid as semi-transparent points. Data are shown separately for each composer, as well as in aggregate. Red diamonds indicate the group mean per condition, and horizontal lines at zero provide a reference for no perceived difference. This illustrated within-subject variation and allows inspection of response consistency across conditions and composers. No clear patterns of preference were observed.

In order to statistically assess the effect of the processing condition, we first account for the nature of the test design, a within-subject test with two factors: processing type and composer, as each subject provided ratings for all three *processing* conditions for each *composer*. Averaging the ratings across composers, allows to narrow the scope to a one-factor analysis, i.e. processing condition. A Friedman test was used to assess whether there were statistically significant differences in similarity ratings across the three processing conditions. The result was not statistically significant ($\chi^2(2) = 0.778$, $p = 0.678$), indicating no overall effect of processing condition. Pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests similarly, did not detect any significant differences: *Original vs. CI Remixed* ($p = 0.875$), *Original vs. CI Preprocessed* ($p = 0.750$), and *CI Remixed vs. CI Preprocessed* ($p = 0.625$). An important note however is that, given the limited number of participants and the absence of repeated trials, the study is underpowered for statistical inference.

4.2 Composer Interviews

The three composers shared several common themes in their interview responses regarding their experience with the CI simulator, while also expressing some differences in their approaches and opinions.

All three composers found that rhythm was the musical element that remained most intact when using the CI simulation, while also agreeing that the CI simulator significantly compromised harmony, melody, and timbre. Consequently, when asked about creating new compositions specifically for the CI simulator, all three composers indicated they would focus on rhythmic elements. Novello suggested defining a new vocabulary for expression, imagining the limitations of music for old phones or nonlinear devices.

None of the composers used voice/speech in their compositions. However, Novello and Maier both thought this could be employed musically with the CI simulator because the transients could be conserved better than sustained instruments.

Based on their experience and expertise, all three had different approaches regarding their remixing strategy. Novello focused on reconstructing the original frequency material, eliminating high bursts, and compensating for internal filtering. Maier chose to emphasize the rhythmic aspect using “ghost notes” on the double bass and removing elements most “sacrificed” by the simulator. Pacorig tried to adjust the equalization to bring out frequencies that would make the original piece more recognizable.

Finally, regarding expressive possibilities while using the CI simulator, Maier believed that by calibrating the compositional/performative aspect on the elements that remain unchanged (rhythm), the possibilities for expression can remain effective, while Pacorig was more discouraged in the simulator’s ability to preserve essential musical elements. Novello felt the CI simulator was quite extreme but he could nevertheless track bpm’s and song construction.

5. DISCUSSION

While no statistically significant differences were observed between the preferences of CI users with respect to the different categories, on visual inspection of the ratings distributions, it appears that the *CI Remixed* and *CI Preprocessed* versions were similar in their comparison to the *Original* versions. This was the case, in particular, for the 2 compositions which were remixed with an equalizer, i.e. Alberto Novello’s and Giorgio Pacorig’s. Somewhat surprisingly, Giovanni Maier’s remix was found to be less preferred than the *CI Preprocessed* version of his original recording. The surprise stems from the fact that he was the only composer who re-performed his original double-bass piece, in an adapted way for the CI. In this process, he shortened the attack of the notes and reduced their sustain, emphasizing the rhythmic part, while removing some of the texture of the original piece. Perhaps this removed some elements that turned out to be appreciated by the CI listeners, especially considering that most of the subjects in our study had unilateral or bimodal configurations, which

Figure 4. CI listening test results aggregated across all subjects and compositions. Ratings are centered (0 = no perceived difference) and compared across the three processing conditions: Original, CI Remixed, and CI Preprocessed.

may have allowed them a good perception of the sound that was cut out, via their better working ears.

Regarding subjective feedback, one individual who participated in the listening test mentioned that the different song excerpts which were compared had very little differences between them, a comment which resonates when looking at the average scores of the ratings distributions seen in Figure 4, centered around 0—“identical”. This circles back to the observation mentioned in Section 3.2.1, that the first 8 principal components accounted for most of the total variance in the CQT data, and therefore the $H_{PCA,8}+P$ preprocessing method produced very similar results to the *Original*. Future work could investigate the effect of a larger spectral reduction by reducing the number of principal components used for reconstruction.

An interesting observation is that the composers’ intuitive adjustments lined up well with the areas of focus in music preprocessing algorithms for CI listeners. In particular, the focus on the rhythmic elements and the reduction of harmonics. However, an interesting theme that recurred in the interviews with the composers was that the limitations of music through CIs can bring with it a new domain for expression, and by calibrating the compositional/performative aspect on the musical elements that remain unchanged and by exploring the new interaction of these elements, the possibilities for expression can remain effective.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A novel study was carried out which investigated the approach of 3 highly experienced music composers when presented with the task of remixing one of their songs through the perspective of a CI user. This was achieved by first developing a stand-alone hardware implementation of a real-time cochlear simulator audio effect, which was used as a monitor probe during the remixing process. An evaluation of the results was carried out through a CCR listening test carried out by 6 individuals wearing CIs, who compared excerpts of the original songs by the three composers, their remixed versions and a preprocessed version of the original with an established algorithm for music enhancement for CI listeners. Although the results were inconsistent, with no statistical differences between the rat-

ings, valuable insights were found and new directions for further work emerged.

Besides the evident direction of increasing the sample size of the study, both in terms of composers but especially with respect to the group of CI listeners, possible future work may include having musicians make new compositions from scratch using the CI simulator and exploring their creative choices. The cochlear simulator listening probe may furthermore be used in a live performance setting, aiming to allow real-time adjustments of musical expression to bridge the gap between normal hearing and CI listeners.

Another future work extension is porting the Bela C++ implementation to a VST version, or a browser-based version. This could allow more reach in terms of recruiting musicians (of various skill levels) who could do their own music adaptation using the cochlear simulator. A significantly increased population could uncover more clear trends and insights.

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